

Variable Name	Type	Variable Label	Value Label
idwoman	int	ID-of-WOMAN	
interview__key	str11	INTERVIEW__KEY-xx-xx-xx-xx-format	
interview__id	str32	INTERVIEW__ID-32-character	
version	str4	VERSION	
incl_doi	str19	Date-Of-Interview~INCLUSION	
incl_idsf	byte	ID-of-Study-midwife~INCLUSION	1 KN; 2 CM; 3 NT; 4 ZE
incl_csps	byte	Centre-de-Sante-et-Promotion-Sociale~INCLUSION	1 Colma I; 2 Colma II; 3 Farakan; 4 Sakaby
incl_w_fname	str18	Woman_First-NAME~INCLUSION	
incl_w_sname	str16	Woman_Last-NAME~INCLUSION	
incl_pass1	int	PASSword-1~INCLUSION	
incl_pass2	int	PASSword-2~INCLUSION	
incl_c_name	str19	Child_NAME~INCLUSION	
incl_c_sex	byte	Child_SEX~INCLUSION	1 M; 2 F
incl_w_age	byte	Woman_AGE~INCLUSION	
incl_deliv	byte	type-of-DELIVERY~INCLUSION	1 L'accouchement vaginal
incl_singleton	byte	SINGLETON-baby-or-twins~INCLUSION	1 Unique
incl_actions__1	byte	ACTIONS-after-delivery__1-immediate-and-complete-drying~INCLUSION	
incl_actions__2	byte	ACTIONS-after-delivery__2-immediate-skin-contact~INCLUSION	
incl_actions__3	byte	ACTIONS-after-delivery__3-delayed-clamping-of-the-cord~INCLUSION	
incl_actions__4	byte	ACTIONS-after-delivery__4-initiation-of-breastfeeding-within-the-first-hour~INCL	
incl_pre_eclampsia	byte	PRE_ECLAMPسيا~INCLUSION	0 Non
incl_systolic_bp	byte	high-SYSTOLIC_Blood-Pressure~INCLUSION	
incl_diastolic_bp	byte	high-DIASTOLIC_Blood-Pressure~INCLUSION	
incl_travel	byte	women-plans-to-travel-in-the-coming-days-after-birth~INCLUSION	0 Non
incl_malf	byte	newborn-congenital-MALFormation~INCLUSION	0 Non
incl_answers	byte	ANSWERS-all-questions~INCLUSION	0 Non; 1 Oui
incl_ic	byte	sIgned-Consent~INCLUSION	1 Oui
incl_reasons_ic	byte	REASONS_not-sIgned-Consent~INCLUSION	
incl_reasons_ic_other	str1	REASONS_not-sIgned-Consent_OTHER~INCLUSION	
incl_name_cc	str51	NAME_head-of-CC~INCLUSION	
incl_ccphone	str8	CC-PHONE-number~INCLUSION	
incl_gps__Latitude	double	GPS_LATITUDE~INCLUSION	
incl_gps__Longitude	double	GPS_LONGITUDE~INCLUSION	
incl_gps__Accuracy	double	GPS_ACCURACY~INCLUSION	
incl_gps__Altitude	double	GPS_ALTITUDE~INCLUSION	
incl_gps__Timestamp	str19	GPS_TIMESTAMP~INCLUSION	
inc_doi2	str10	Date-Of-Interview-2~INCLUSION	
dol1_wspecial__1	byte	Woman-SPECIAL__1-RAS~Day-Of-Life-1	

Variable Name	Type	Variable Label	Value Label
dol1_wspecial__2	byte	Woman-SPECIAL__2-blind~Day-Of-Life-1	
dol1_wspecial__3	byte	Woman-SPECIAL__3-deaf~Day-Of-Life-1	
dol1_wspecial__4	byte	Woman-SPECIAL__4-deaf-mute~Day-Of-Life-1	
dol1_wspecial__5	byte	Woman-SPECIAL__5-mental-illness~Day-Of-Life-1	
dol1_wspecial__6	byte	Woman-SPECIAL__6-physical-disability~Day-Of-Life-1	
dol1_wspecial__88	byte	Woman-SPECIAL__88-other~Day-Of-Life-1	
dol1_wspecial_other	str1	Woman-SPECIAL__OTHER~Day-Of-Life-1	
dol1_wpreg	byte	Woman-number-of-PREGnancies~Day-Of-Life-1	
dol1_wdeliv	byte	Woman-number-of-children-DELIVeRed-above-6mo~Day-Of-Life-1	
dol1_wsb	byte	Woman-number-of-StillBirths~Day-Of-Life-1	
dol1_wmc	byte	Woman-number-of-MisCarriages~Day-Of-Life-1	
dol1_wcs	byte	Woman-number-of-C-Sections~Day-Of-Life-1	
dol1_wchild	byte	Woman-number-of-CHILDren~Day-Of-Life-1	
dol1_wchildu5	byte	Woman-number-of-CHILDren-Under-5~Day-Of-Life-1	
dol1_wchildlb_dmy	str10	Woman-CHILD-Last-one-Birth_DayMonthYear~Day-Of-Life-1	
dol1_wchildlb_my	str7	Woman-CHILD-Last-one-Birth_MonthYear~Day-Of-Life-1	
dol1_wchildlb_y	str4	Woman-CHILD-Last-one-Birth_Year~Day-Of-Life-1	
dol1_reanim2	byte	was-child-REANIMated-at-delivery~Day-Of-Life-1	0 No
dol1_reanim_min2	byte	REANIMation-time_in-minutes~Day-Of-Life-1	
dol1_heure_dubo	str19	HEURE-hour-and-date_DUBOwiz-score~Day-Of-Life-1	
dol1_posture	byte	dubo-POSTURE~Day-Of-Life-1	
dol1_wrist	byte	dubo-WRIST-square-window~Day-Of-Life-1	
dol1_ankle	byte	dubo-ANKLE-dorsiflexion~Day-Of-Life-1	
dol1_arm	byte	dubo-ARMS~Day-Of-Life-1	
dol1_leg	byte	dubo-LEGS~Day-Of-Life-1	
dol1_popliteal	byte	dubo-POPLITEAL-angle~Day-Of-Life-1	
dol1_scarf	byte	dubo-SCARF-sign~Day-Of-Life-1	
dol1_heel	byte	dubo-HEEL-to-ear~Day-Of-Life-1	
dol1_headlag	byte	dubo-HEAD-LAG~Day-Of-Life-1	
dol1_ventral	byte	dubo-VENTRAL-suspension~Day-Of-Life-1	
dol1_edema	byte	dubo-EDEMA~Day-Of-Life-1	0 œdèmes évidents aux mains et aux pieds, prenant le godet au niveau du tibia; 1 pas d'œdèmes évidents, mais godet + sur le tibia; 2 pas d'oedème
dol1_skintexture	byte	dubo-SKIN-TEXTURE~Day-Of-Life-1	1 Fine et lisse; 2 lisse, épaisseur intermédiaire, éruption ou desquamation superficielle; 3 épaissement modéré, fissures superficielles et desquamation surtout au niveau des mains et des pieds; 4 épaisse, parcheminée, fissures

Variable Name	Type	Variable Label	Value Label
doll_skincolor	byte	dubo-SKIN-COLOR~Day-Of-Life-1	0 rouge foncé; 1 uniformément rose; 2 rose pâle; variable sur le corps; 3 pâle; uniquement du rose sur les oreilles, les lèvres, les paumes ou la plante des pieds
doll_skinopacity	byte	dubo-SKIN-OPACITY~Day-Of-Life-1	1 Veines et vaisseaux affluents visibles 2 quelques gros vaisseaux visibles sur l'abdomen 3 Quelques gros vaisseaux difficilement visibles sur l'abdomen 4 pas de vaisseaux sanguins visibles
doll_lanugo	byte	dubo-LANUGO~Day-Of-Life-1	0 absent 1 abondant; long et épais sur tout le dos 2 clairsemé, surtout sur le bas du dos 3 peu abondant, plaques dénudées 4 plus de la moitié du dos dégarni de poils
doll_plantar	byte	ballard-PLANTAR-surface~Day-Of-Life-1	0 pas de plis 1 légères marques rouges sur la moitié antérieure de la semelle 2 marques rouges nettes sur > 1/3 antérieur 3 sillons sur plus du 1/3 antérieur 4 sillons profonds définis sur plus du 1/3 antérieur
doll_nipple	byte	dubo-NIPPLE-formation~Day-Of-Life-1	0 mamelon à peine visible; pas d'aréole 1 mamelon bien défini; aréole lisse et plate, diamètre < 7,5 mm 2 aréole grenue, non surélevée diamètre > 7.5mm 3 aréole grenue, bords surélevés et diamètre >7.5mm
doll_breast	byte	ballard-BREAST-size~Day-Of-Life-1	0 pas de tissu mammaire palpable 1 tissu mammaire d'un ou des deux côtés < 5 mm de diamètre 2 tissu mammaire des 2 côtés; 1 ou les 2 de 5 à 10 mm 3 tissu mammaire des deux côtés; 1 ou les 2 > 10 mm
doll_eye_earform	byte	dubo-EYE_EAR-FORM~Day-Of-Life-1	1 bord partiellement ourlé 2 partie supérieure du lobe partiellement ourlée 3 Totalement ou bien ourlée
doll_eye_earfirmness	byte	dubo-EYE_EAR-FIRMNESS~Day-Of-Life-1	1 lobe mou, pliable, reprend lentement sa position 2 cartilage présent, mou par endroits, reprend facilement sa position 3 cartilage ferme, reprend instantanément sa position
doll_genitals_m	byte	ballard-GENITALS_Male~Day-Of-Life-1	0 testicules non présents dans le scrotum 1 un testicule au moins haut placé dans le scrotum 2 au moins un testicule descendu
doll_genitals_f	byte	ballard-GENITALS_Female~Day-Of-Life-1	0 grandes lèvres bien séparées, petites lèvres dépassant 1 les grandes lèvres recouvrent presque les petites lèvres 2 les grandes lèvres recouvrent complètement les petites lèvres
DUBO_sum_girl	double	DUBO_SUM-score_GIRL	
DUBO_sum_boy	double	DUBO_SUM-score_BOY	
doll_DUBO_GA_boy	double	DUBO-score_Gestational-Age-in-wk_BOY~Day-Of-Life-1	
doll_DUBO_GA_girl	double	DUBO-score_Gestational-Age-in-wk_GIRL~Day-Of-Life-1	
pic_dubo	str14	PICTure_DUBOwitz-score-card	

Variable Name	Type	Variable Label	Value Label
dol1_ddd_yn	byte	Date-of-Dernieres-Regles-last-menstruation_Yes-No~Day-Of-Life-1	0 Non; 1 Oui
dol1_ddd_dmy	str10	Date-of-Dernieres-Regles-last-menstruation_DayMonthYear~Day-Of-Life-1	
dol1_nr_cpn	byte	NumbeR-of_CPN-anc-done~Day-Of-Life-1	
dol1_hu_cpn1	byte	HU-fundal-height-known_at-CPN-anc1~Day-Of-Life-1	0 Non; 1 Oui
dol1_hu_date1	str10	HU-fundal-height-known_DATE-of-anc1~Day-Of-Life-1	
dol1_hu_cpn1_cm	byte	HU-fundal-height_at-CPN-anc1_in-CM~Day-Of-Life-1	
dol1_hu_cpn2	byte	HU-fundal-height-known_at-CPN-anc2~Day-Of-Life-1	0 Non; 1 Oui
dol1_hu_date2	str10	HU-fundal-height-known_DATE-of-anc2~Day-Of-Life-1	
dol1_hu_cpn2_cm	byte	HU-fundal-height_at-CPN-anc2_in-CM~Day-Of-Life-1	
dol1_hu_cpn3	byte	HU-fundal-height-known_at-CPN-anc3~Day-Of-Life-1	0 Non; 1 Oui
dol1_hu_date3	str10	HU-fundal-height-known_DATE-of-anc3~Day-Of-Life-1	
dol1_hu_cpn3_cm	byte	HU-fundal-height_at-CPN-anc3_in-CM~Day-Of-Life-1	
dol1_hu_cpn4	byte	HU-fundal-height-known_at-CPN-anc4~Day-Of-Life-1	0 Non; 1 Oui
dol1_hu_date4	str10	HU-fundal-height-known_DATE-of-anc4~Day-Of-Life-1	
dol1_hu_cpn4_cm	byte	HU-fundal-height_at-CPN-anc4_in-CM~Day-Of-Life-1	
dol1_hu_cpn5	byte	HU-fundal-height-known_at-CPN-anc5~Day-Of-Life-1	0 Non; 1 Oui
dol1_hu_date5	str10	HU-fundal-height-known_DATE-of-anc5~Day-Of-Life-1	
dol1_hu_cpn5_cm	byte	HU-fundal-height_at-CPN-anc5_in-CM~Day-Of-Life-1	
dol1_hu_cpn6	byte	HU-fundal-height-known_at-CPN-anc6~Day-Of-Life-1	0 Non; 1 Oui
dol1_hu_date6	str10	HU-fundal-height-known_DATE-of-anc6~Day-Of-Life-1	
dol1_hu_cpn6_cm	byte	HU-fundal-height_at-CPN-anc6_in-CM~Day-Of-Life-1	
dol1_hu_cpn7	byte	HU-fundal-height-known_at-CPN-anc7~Day-Of-Life-1	0 Non; 1 Oui
dol1_hu_date7	str10	HU-fundal-height-known_DATE-of-anc7~Day-Of-Life-1	
dol1_hu_cpn7_cm	byte	HU-fundal-height_at-CPN-anc7_in-CM~Day-Of-Life-1	
dol1_hu_cpn8	byte	HU-fundal-height-known_at-CPN-anc8~Day-Of-Life-1	0 Non; 1 Oui
dol1_hu_date8	str10	HU-fundal-height-known_DATE-of-anc8~Day-Of-Life-1	
dol1_hu_cpn8_cm	byte	HU-fundal-height_at-CPN-anc8_in-CM~Day-Of-Life-1	
dol1_deliv_yn	byte	expected-DELIVery-date-known_Yes-No~Day-Of-Life-1	0 Non; 1 Oui
dol1_deliv_est	byte	DELIVery-date_ESTImation-method~Day-Of-Life-1	1 Gestogramme; 2 Formule de calcul; 3 Graphique; 99 Pas connu
dol1_deliv_dmy	str10	expected-DELIVery-date_DayMonthYear~Day-Of-Life-1	
dol1_sp	byte	SP-malaria-prevention~Day-Of-Life-1	0 Non; 1 Oui
dol1_alb	byte	ALB-received-deworming~Day-Of-Life-1	0 Non; 1 Oui
dol1_anamnese	byte	ANAMNESE-deliver-before-check~Day-Of-Life-1	1 RAS; 2 Plaintes à signaler
dol1_anamnese_other	str18	ANAMNESE-deliver-before-check_OTHER~Day-Of-Life-1	
dol1_type_deliv	byte	TYPE-of_DELIVery~Day-Of-Life-1	1 Eutocique; 2 Dystocique
dol1_deliv_int	byte	DELIVery_INTervention~Day-Of-Life-1	1 Pas d'intervention; 5 Episiotomie

Variable Name	Type	Variable Label	Value Label
dol1_deliv	byte	DELIVery~Day-Of-Life-1	1 Normale; 99 Ne sait pas
dol1_w_height1	double	Woman_HEIGHT-1~Day-Of-Life-1	
dol1_w_height2	double	Woman_HEIGHT-2~Day-Of-Life-1	
dol1_w_height3	double	Woman_HEIGHT-3~Day-Of-Life-1	
dol1_w_muac1	int	Woman_MUAC-1~Day-Of-Life-1	
dol1_w_muac2	int	Woman_MUAC-2~Day-Of-Life-1	
dol1_w_muac3	byte	Woman_MUAC-3~Day-Of-Life-1	
dol1_dob	str10	Date-Of-Birth~Day-Of-Life-1	
dol1_time	str5	TIME-of-birth~Day-Of-Life-1	
dol1_dom	str10	Date-Of-anthropometry-Measurement~Day-Of-Life-1	
dol1_hom	str5	Hour-Of-anthropometry-Measurement~Day-Of-Life-1	
dol1_weight1	double	child-birth-WEIGHT-1~Day-Of-Life-1	
dol1_weight2	double	child-birth-WEIGHT-2~Day-Of-Life-1	
dol1_weight3	double	child-birth-WEIGHT-3~Day-Of-Life-1	
dol1_height1	double	child-birth-HEIGHT-1~Day-Of-Life-1	
dol1_height2	double	child-birth-HEIGHT-2~Day-Of-Life-1	
dol1_height3	double	child-birth-HEIGHT-3~Day-Of-Life-1	
dol1_muac1	int	child-birth-MUAC-1~Day-Of-Life-1	
dol1_muac2	int	child-birth-MUAC-2~Day-Of-Life-1	
dol1_muac3	byte	child-birth-MUAC-3~Day-Of-Life-1	
dol1_hc1	double	child-birth-Head-Circumference-1~Day-Of-Life-1	
dol1_hc2	double	child-birth-Head-Circumference-2~Day-Of-Life-1	
dol1_hc3	double	child-birth-Head-Circumference-2~Day-Of-Life-1	
dol1_cc1	double	child-birth-Chest-Circumference-1~Day-Of-Life-1	
dol1_cc2	double	child-birth-Chest-Circumference-2~Day-Of-Life-1	
dol1_cc3	double	child-birth-Chest-Circumference-3~Day-Of-Life-1	
dol1_apgar1	byte	APGAR-score-at-delivery-1-minutes~Day-Of-Life-1	
dol1_colostrum1h	byte	COLOSTRUM-within-1-hour~Day-Of-Life-1	0 Non; 1 Oui
pic_fichebio	str18	PICTure_FICHEBIO	
dol1_bf	byte	exclusive-Breast-Feeding~Day-Of-Life-1	1 Oui
dol1_bf_freq	byte	exclusive-Breast-Feeding_FREQUency~Day-Of-Life-1	1 1-3 fois au cours des dernières 24 heures 2 4-7 fois au cours des dernières 24 heures
dol1_bf_reason	byte	end-exclusive-Breast-Feeding_REASON~Day-Of-Life-1	
dol1_bf_reason_other	str1	end-exclusive-Breast-Feeding_REASON_OTHER~Day-Of-Life-1	
dol1_liq	byte	giving-LIQuids-during-breastfeeding~Day-Of-Life-1	0 Non
dol1_liq_freq	byte	giving-LIQuids-during-breastfeeding_FREQUency~Day-Of-Life-1	
dol1_solid	byte	giving-SOLIDs-during-breastfeeding~Day-Of-Life-1	0 Non
dol1_solid_freq	byte	giving-SOLIDs-during-breastfeeding_FREQUency~Day-Of-Life-1	

Variable Name	Type	Variable Label	Value Label
dol1_temp	double	body-TEMPERature-of-child~Day-Of-Life-1	
dol1_cd1	byte	Child-Disease-1-fever~Day-Of-Life-1	0 Non; 1 Oui
dol1_cd2	byte	Child-Disease-2-diarrhea~Day-Of-Life-1	0 Non; 1 Oui
dol1_cd3	byte	Child-Disease-3-vomit~Day-Of-Life-1	0 Non; 1 Oui
dol1_cd4	byte	Child-Disease-4-cough~Day-Of-Life-1	0 Non; 1 Oui
dol1_cd5	byte	Child-Disease-5-running-nose~Day-Of-Life-1	0 Non; 1 Oui
dol1_cd6	byte	Child-Disease-6-difficult-breathing~Day-Of-Life-1	0 Non; 1 Oui
dol1_cd7	byte	Child-Disease-7-grunting~Day-Of-Life-1	0 Non; 1 Oui
dol1_cd8	byte	Child-Disease-8-skin-lesions~Day-Of-Life-1	0 Non; 1 Oui
dol1_cd9	byte	Child-Disease-9-others~Day-Of-Life-1	0 Non; 1 Oui
dol1_cd9a	str1	morbidity-Child-Disease-9-All~Day-Of-Life-1	
dol1_consul__0	byte	morbidity-CONSULT__0-non~Day-Of-Life-1	
dol1_consul__1	byte	morbidity-CONSULT__1-csps~Day-Of-Life-1	
dol1_consul__2	byte	morbidity-CONSULT__2-hospital~Day-Of-Life-1	
dol1_consul__3	byte	morbidity-CONSULT__3-traditional-practitioner~Day-Of-Life-1	
dol1_consul__4	byte	morbidity-CONSULT__4-ASBC~Day-Of-Life-1	
dol1_consul__5	byte	morbidity-CONSULT__5-friend~Day-Of-Life-1	
dol1_consul__6	byte	morbidity-CONSULT__6-family-member~Day-Of-Life-1	
dol1_consul__88	byte	morbidity-CONSULT__88-other~Day-Of-Life-1	
dol1_consul__99	byte	morbidity-CONSULT__99-unknown~Day-Of-Life-1	
dol1_consul_other	str1	morbidity-CONSULT__OTHER~Day-Of-Life-1	
dol1_treat__0	byte	TREATment__0-non~Day-Of-Life-1	
dol1_treat__1	byte	TREATment__1-prescribed-by-health-worker~Day-Of-Life-1	
dol1_treat__2	byte	TREATment__2-self-medication~Day-Of-Life-1	
dol1_treat__3	byte	TREATment__3-traditional-treatment~Day-Of-Life-1	
dol1_treat__4	byte	TREATment__4-treatment-for-malnutrition~Day-Of-Life-1	
dol1_treat__88	byte	TREATment__88-others~Day-Of-Life-1	
dol1_treat_other	str1	TREATment__OTHER~Day-Of-Life-1	
dol1_result	byte	diagnosis-child-morbidity-RESULT~Day-Of-Life-1	
dol1_diagn__1	byte	DIAGNosis-child-morbidity__1-malaria~Day-Of-Life-1	
dol1_diagn__2	byte	DIAGNosis-child-morbidity__2-broncho-pneumonia~Day-Of-Life-1	
dol1_diagn__3	byte	DIAGNosis-child-morbidity__3-bacterial/viral/parasitic-diarrhea~Day-Of-Life-1	
dol1_diagn__4	byte	DIAGNosis-child-morbidity__4-dengue-fever~Day-Of-Life-1	
dol1_diagn__5	byte	DIAGNosis-child-morbidity__5-dehydration~Day-Of-Life-1	
dol1_diagn__6	byte	DIAGNosis-child-morbidity__6-malnutrition~Day-Of-Life-1	
dol1_diagn__99	byte	DIAGNosis-child-morbidity__99-unknown~Day-Of-Life-1	
dol1_diagn__88	byte	DIAGNosis-child-morbidity__88-others~Day-Of-Life-1	

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dol1_diagn_other	str1	DIAGNosis-child-morbidity__OTHER~Day-Of-Life-1	
dol1_hosp	byte	HOSPitalization-child~Day-Of-Life-1	0 Non; 1 Oui
dol1_doi_check	str19	Date-Of-Interview_CHECK~Day-Of-Life-1	
sssys_irnd	double	Random-number-in-the-range-0-1-associated-with-interview	
has_errors	byte	HAS__how-many-errors	
interview__status	int	INTERVIEW__STATUS	100 Completed
assignment__id	int	ASSIGNMENT__ID	
pic_dubo2	str15	PICTure_DUBOwitz-score-card-2	
dol1_w_weight1	double	Woman_WEIGHT-1~Day-Of-Life-1	
dol1_w_weight2	double	Woman_WEIGHT-2~Day-Of-Life-1	
dol1_w_weight3	double	Woman_WEIGHT-3~Day-Of-Life-1	
round	float	ROUND	
dol2_doi	str19	Date-Of-Interview~Day-Of-Life-2	
dol2_idsf	byte	ID-of-Study-midwiFe~Day-Of-Life-2	5 CA-Assanatou; 6 CA-Aissata; 7 WN; 8 KA; 9 KD; 10 ON; 11 NS; 12 OM
dol2_csps	byte	Centre-de-Sante-et-Promotion-Sociale~Day-Of-Life-2	1 Colma I; 2 Colma II; 3 Farakan; 4 Accart
dol2_w_name	str25	Woman_NAM~Day-Of-Life-2	
dol2_pass1	int	PASSword-1~Day-Of-Life-2	
dol2_pass2	int	PASSword-2~Day-Of-Life-2	
dol2_c_name	str21	Child_NAME~Day-Of-Life-2	
dol2_c_sex	byte	Child_SEX~Day-Of-Life-2	1 M; 2 F
dol2_dom	str10	Date-Of-anthropometry-Measurement~Day-Of-Life-2	
dol2_hom	str7	Hour-Of-anthropometry-Measurement~Day-Of-Life-2	
dol2_weight1	double	child-birth-WEIGHT-1~Day-Of-Life-2	
dol2_weight2	double	child-birth-WEIGHT-2~Day-Of-Life-2	
dol2_weight3	double	child-birth-WEIGHT-3~Day-Of-Life-2	
dol2_bf	byte	exclusive-Breast-Feeding~Day-Of-Life-2	0 Non; 1 Oui
dol2_bf_freq	byte	exclusive-Breast-Feeding_FREQuency~Day-Of-Life-2	1 1-3 fois au cours des dernières 24 heures 2 4-7 fois au cours des dernières 24 heures 3 7-9 fois au cours des dernières 24 heures 4 Plus que 9 fois au cours des dernières 24 heures
dol2_bf_reason	byte	end-exclusive-Breast-Feeding_REASON~Day-Of-Life-2	1 Difficulté d'allaiter l'enfant 2 La mère dit n'avoir pas assez de lait
dol2_bf_reason_other	str1	end-exclusive-Breast-Feeding_REASON_OTHER~Day-Of-Life-2	
dol2_liq	byte	giving-LIQuids-during-breastfeeding~Day-Of-Life-2	0 Non; 1 Oui
dol2_liq_freq	byte	giving-LIQuids-during-breastfeeding_FREQuency~Day-Of-Life-2	1 1 fois au cours des dernières 24 heures 2 2 fois au cours des dernières 24 heures
dol2_solid	byte	giving-SOLIDs-during-breastfeeding~Day-Of-Life-2	0 Non; 1 Oui
dol2_solid_freq	byte	giving-SOLIDs-during-breastfeeding_FREQuency~Day-Of-Life-2	1 1 fois au cours des dernières 24 heures
dol2_temp	double	body-TEMPERature-of-child~Day-Of-Life-2	

Variable Name	Type	Variable Label	Value Label
dol2_cd1	byte	Child-Disease-1-fever~Day-Of-Life-2	0 Non; 1 Oui
dol2_cd2	byte	Child-Disease-2-diarrhea~Day-Of-Life-2	0 Non; 1 Oui
dol2_cd3	byte	Child-Disease-3-vomit~Day-Of-Life-2	0 Non; 1 Oui
dol2_cd4	byte	Child-Disease-4-cough~Day-Of-Life-2	0 Non; 1 Oui
dol2_cd5	byte	Child-Disease-5-running-nose~Day-Of-Life-2	0 Non; 1 Oui
dol2_cd6	byte	Child-Disease-6-difficult-breathing~Day-Of-Life-2	0 Non; 1 Oui
dol2_cd7	byte	Child-Disease-7-grunting~Day-Of-Life-2	0 Non; 1 Oui
dol2_cd8	byte	Child-Disease-8-skin-lesions~Day-Of-Life-2	0 Non; 1 Oui
dol2_cd9	byte	Child-Disease-9-others~Day-Of-Life-2	0 Non; 1 Oui
dol2_cd9a	str6	morbidity-Child-Disease-9-All~Day-Of-Life-2	
dol2_consul__0	byte	morbidity-CONSULT__0-non~Day-Of-Life-2	
dol2_consul__1	byte	morbidity-CONSULT__1-csps~Day-Of-Life-2	
dol2_consul__2	byte	morbidity-CONSULT__2-hospital~Day-Of-Life-2	
dol2_consul__3	byte	morbidity-CONSULT__3-traditional-practitioner~Day-Of-Life-2	
dol2_consul__4	byte	morbidity-CONSULT__4-ASBC~Day-Of-Life-2	
dol2_consul__5	byte	morbidity-CONSULT__5-friend~Day-Of-Life-2	
dol2_consul__6	byte	morbidity-CONSULT__6-family-member~Day-Of-Life-2	
dol2_consul__88	byte	morbidity-CONSULT__88-other~Day-Of-Life-2	
dol2_consul__99	byte	morbidity-CONSULT__99-unknown~Day-Of-Life-2	
dol2_consul_other	str1	morbidity-CONSULT__OTHER~Day-Of-Life-2	
dol2_treat__0	byte	TREATment__0-non~Day-Of-Life-2	
dol2_treat__1	byte	TREATment__1-prescribed-by-health-worker~Day-Of-Life-2	
dol2_treat__2	byte	TREATment__2-self-medication~Day-Of-Life-2	
dol2_treat__3	byte	TREATment__3-traditional-treatment~Day-Of-Life-2	
dol2_treat__4	byte	TREATment__4-treatment-for-malnutrition~Day-Of-Life-2	
dol2_treat__88	byte	TREATment__88-others~Day-Of-Life-2	
dol2_treat_other	str1	TREATment__OTHER~Day-Of-Life-2	
dol2_result	byte	diagnosis-child-morbidity-RESULT~Day-Of-Life-2	1 Traitement toujours en cours
dol2_diagn__1	byte	DIAGNosis-child-morbidity__1-malaria~Day-Of-Life-2	
dol2_diagn__2	byte	DIAGNosis-child-morbidity__2-broncho-pneumonia~Day-Of-Life-2	
dol2_diagn__3	byte	DIAGNosis-child-morbidity__3-bacterial/viral/parasitic-diarrhea~Day-Of-Life-2	
dol2_diagn__4	byte	DIAGNosis-child-morbidity__4-dengue-fever~Day-Of-Life-2	
dol2_diagn__5	byte	DIAGNosis-child-morbidity__5-dehydration~Day-Of-Life-2	
dol2_diagn__6	byte	DIAGNosis-child-morbidity__6-malnutrition~Day-Of-Life-2	
dol2_diagn__99	byte	DIAGNosis-child-morbidity__99-unknown~Day-Of-Life-2	
dol2_diagn__88	byte	DIAGNosis-child-morbidity__88-others~Day-Of-Life-2	
dol2_diagn_other	str83	DIAGNosis-child-morbidity__OTHER~Day-Of-Life-2	

Variable Name	Type	Variable Label	Value Label
dol2_hosp	byte	HOSPitalization-child~Day-Of-Life-2	0 Non
dol2_done	byte	did-the-visit-hone~Day-Of-Life-2	1 Oui
dol2_reason_no	byte	REASON-of_NOT-visit~Day-Of-Life-2	
dol2_reason_other	str1	REASON-of_NOT-visit-OTHER~Day-Of-Life-2	
dol2_notes_yn	byte	NOTES-end-of-study_Yes-No~Day-Of-Life-2	0 Non; 1 Oui
dol2_notes	str94	NOTES-end-of-study ~Day-Of-Life-2	
dol3_doi	str19	Date-Of-Interview~Day-Of-Life-3	
dol3_idsf	byte	ID-of-Study-midwiFe~Day-Of-Life-3	5 CA-Assanatu; 6 CA-Aissata; 7 WN; 8 KA; 9 KD; 10 ON; 11 NS; 12 OM
dol3_csps	byte	Centre-de-Sante-et-Promotion-Sociale~Day-Of-Life-3	1 Colma I; 2 Colma II; 3 Farakan; 4 Sakaby
dol3_w_name	str25	Woman_NAM~Day-Of-Life-3	
dol3_pass1	int	PASSword-1~Day-Of-Life-3	
dol3_pass2	int	PASSword-2~Day-Of-Life-3	
dol3_c_name	str24	Child_NAME~Day-Of-Life-3	
dol3_c_sex	byte	Child_SEX~Day-Of-Life-3	1 M; 2 F
dol3_dom	str10	Date-Of-anthropometry-Measurement~Day-Of-Life-3	
dol3_hom	str7	Hour-Of-anthropometry-Measurement~Day-Of-Life-3	
dol3_weight1	double	child-birth-WEIGHT-1~Day-Of-Life-3	
dol3_weight2	double	child-birth-WEIGHT-2~Day-Of-Life-3	
dol3_weight3	double	child-birth-WEIGHT-3~Day-Of-Life-3	
dol3_bf	byte	exclusive-Breast-Feeding~Day-Of-Life-3	0 Non; 1 Oui
dol3_bf_freq	byte	exclusive-Breast-Feeding_FREQuency~Day-Of-Life-3	1 1-3 fois au cours des dernières 24 heures 2 4-7 fois au cours des dernières 24 heures 3 7-9 fois au cours des dernières 24 heures 4 Plus que 9 fois au cours des dernières 24 heures
dol3_bf_reason	byte	end-exclusive-Breast-Feeding_REASON~Day-Of-Life-3	2 La mère dit n'avoir pas assez de lait
dol3_bf_reason_other	str1	end-exclusive-Breast-Feeding_REASON_OTHER~Day-Of-Life-3	
dol3_liq	byte	giving-LIQuids-during-breastfeeding~Day-Of-Life-3	0 Non; 1 Oui
dol3_liq_freq	byte	giving-LIQuids-during-breastfeeding_FREQuency~Day-Of-Life-3	1 1 fois au cours des dernières 24 heures 2 2 fois au cours des dernières 24 heures 3 3 fois au cours des dernières 24 heures 4 Plus que au cours des dernières 24 heures
dol3_solid	byte	giving-SOLIDs-during-breastfeeding~Day-Of-Life-3	0 Non; 1 Oui
dol3_solid_freq	byte	giving-SOLIDs-during-breastfeeding_FREQuency~Day-Of-Life-3	1 1 fois au cours des dernières 24 heures
dol3_temp	double	body-TEMPERature-of-child~Day-Of-Life-3	
dol3_cd1	byte	Child-Disease-1-fever~Day-Of-Life-3	0 Non; 1 Oui
dol3_cd2	byte	Child-Disease-2-diarrhea~Day-Of-Life-3	0 Non; 1 Oui
dol3_cd3	byte	Child-Disease-3-vomit~Day-Of-Life-3	0 Non; 1 Oui
dol3_cd4	byte	Child-Disease-4-cough~Day-Of-Life-3	0 Non; 1 Oui
dol3_cd5	byte	Child-Disease-5-running-nose~Day-Of-Life-3	0 Non; 1 Oui
dol3_cd6	byte	Child-Disease-6-difficult-breathing~Day-Of-Life-3	0 Non; 1 Oui

Variable Name	Type	Variable Label	Value Label
dol3_cd7	byte	Child-Disease-7-grunting~Day-Of-Life-3	0 Non; 1 Oui
dol3_cd8	byte	Child-Disease-8-skin-lesions~Day-Of-Life-3	0 Non; 1 Oui
dol3_cd9	byte	Child-Disease-9-others~Day-Of-Life-3	0 Non; 1 Oui
dol3_cd9a	str28	morbidity-Child-Disease-9-All~Day-Of-Life-3	
dol3_consul__0	byte	morbidity-CONSULT__0-non~Day-Of-Life-3	
dol3_consul__1	byte	morbidity-CONSULT__1-csps~Day-Of-Life-3	
dol3_consul__2	byte	morbidity-CONSULT__2-hospital~Day-Of-Life-3	
dol3_consul__3	byte	morbidity-CONSULT__3-traditional-practitioner~Day-Of-Life-3	
dol3_consul__4	byte	morbidity-CONSULT__4-ASBC~Day-Of-Life-3	
dol3_consul__5	byte	morbidity-CONSULT__5-friend~Day-Of-Life-3	
dol3_consul__6	byte	morbidity-CONSULT__6-family-member~Day-Of-Life-3	
dol3_consul__88	byte	morbidity-CONSULT__88-other~Day-Of-Life-3	
dol3_consul__99	byte	morbidity-CONSULT__99-unknown~Day-Of-Life-3	
dol3_consul_other	str1	morbidity-CONSULT__OTHER~Day-Of-Life-3	
dol3_treat__0	byte	TREATment__0-non~Day-Of-Life-3	
dol3_treat__1	byte	TREATment__1-prescribed-by-health-worker~Day-Of-Life-3	
dol3_treat__2	byte	TREATment__2-self-medication~Day-Of-Life-3	
dol3_treat__3	byte	TREATment__3-traditional-treatment~Day-Of-Life-3	
dol3_treat__4	byte	TREATment__4-treatment-for-malnutrition~Day-Of-Life-3	
dol3_treat__88	byte	TREATment__88-others~Day-Of-Life-3	
dol3_treat_other	str1	TREATment__OTHER~Day-Of-Life-3	
dol3_result	byte	diagnosis-child-morbidity-RESULT~Day-Of-Life-3	1 Traitement toujours en cours
dol3_diagn__1	byte	DIAGNosis-child-morbidity__1-malaria~Day-Of-Life-3	
dol3_diagn__2	byte	DIAGNosis-child-morbidity__2-broncho-pneumonia~Day-Of-Life-3	
dol3_diagn__3	byte	DIAGNosis-child-morbidity__3-bacterial/viral/parasitic-diarrhea~Day-Of-Life-3	
dol3_diagn__4	byte	DIAGNosis-child-morbidity__4-dengue-fever~Day-Of-Life-3	
dol3_diagn__5	byte	DIAGNosis-child-morbidity__5-dehydration~Day-Of-Life-3	
dol3_diagn__6	byte	DIAGNosis-child-morbidity__6-malnutrition~Day-Of-Life-3	
dol3_diagn__99	byte	DIAGNosis-child-morbidity__99-unknown~Day-Of-Life-3	
dol3_diagn__88	byte	DIAGNosis-child-morbidity__88-others~Day-Of-Life-3	
dol3_diagn_other	str25	DIAGNosis-child-morbidity__OTHER~Day-Of-Life-3	
dol3_hosp	byte	HOSPitalization-child~Day-Of-Life-3	0 Non
fs_1a	byte	Food-Security_1A-fear-insufficient-food	0 Non; 1 Oui
fs_1b	byte	Food-Security_1A-frequency-of-fear-insufficient-food	1 Rarement (1 à 2 fois ces 4 dernières semaines) 2 Parfois (3 à 10 fois ces 4 dernières semaines) 3 Souvent (plus de 10 fois ces 4 dernières semaines)
fs_2a	byte	Food-Security_2A-not-eating-preferred-food	0 Non; 1 Oui

Variable Name	Type	Variable Label	Value Label
fs_2b	byte	Food-Security_2B-frequency-of-not-eating-preferred-food	1 Rarement (1 à 2 fois ces 4 dernières semaines) 2 Parfois (3 à 10 fois ces 4 dernières semaines) 3 Souvent (plus de 10 fois ces 4 dernières semaines)
fs_3a	byte	Food-Security_3A-limited-food-diversity	0 Non; 1 Oui
fs_3b	byte	Food-Security_3B-frequency-of-limited-food-diversity	1 Rarement (1 à 2 fois ces 4 dernières semaines) 2 Parfois (3 à 10 fois ces 4 dernières semaines) 3 Souvent (plus de 10 fois ces 4 dernières semaines)
fs_4a	byte	Food-Security_4A-undesirable-food	0 Non; 1 Oui
fs_4b	byte	Food-Security_4B-frequency-of-undesirable-food	1 Rarement (1 à 2 fois ces 4 dernières semaines) 2 Parfois (3 à 10 fois ces 4 dernières semaines) 3 Souvent (plus de 10 fois ces 4 dernières semaines)
fs_5a	byte	Food-Security_5A-smaller-meals	0 Non; 1 Oui
fs_5b	byte	Food-Security_5B-frequency-of-smaller-meals	1 Rarement (1 à 2 fois ces 4 dernières semaines) 2 Parfois (3 à 10 fois ces 4 dernières semaines) 3 Souvent (plus de 10 fois ces 4 dernières semaines)
fs_6a	byte	Food-Security_6A-fewer-meals	0 Non; 1 Oui
fs_6b	byte	Food-Security_6B-frequency-of-fewer-meals	1 Rarement (1 à 2 fois ces 4 dernières semaines) 2 Parfois (3 à 10 fois ces 4 dernières semaines) 3 Souvent (plus de 10 fois ces 4 dernières semaines)
fs_7a	byte	Food-Security_7A-no-food	0 Non; 1 Oui
fs_7b	byte	Food-Security_7B-frequency-of-no-food	1 Rarement (1 à 2 fois ces 4 dernières semaines) 2 Parfois (3 à 10 fois ces 4 dernières semaines) 3 Souvent (plus de 10 fois ces 4 dernières semaines)
fs_8a	byte	Food-Security_8A-sleep-without-eating	0 Non; 1 Oui
fs_8b	byte	Food-Security_8B-frequency-of-sleep-without-eating	1 Rarement (1 à 2 fois ces 4 dernières semaines) 2 Parfois (3 à 10 fois ces 4 dernières semaines) 3 Souvent (plus de 10 fois ces 4 dernières semaines)
fs_9a	byte	Food-Security_9A-no-food-night-and-day	0 Non; 1 Oui
fs_9b	byte	Food-Security_9B-frequency-of-no-food-night-and-day	1 Rarement (1 à 2 fois ces 4 dernières semaines) 2 Parfois (3 à 10 fois ces 4 dernières semaines) 3 Souvent (plus de 10 fois ces 4 dernières semaines)
hh_water	byte	HouseHold_WATER-source	1 Eau du robinet / borne fontaine 2 Puits à pompe ou forage 3 Puits (à grand diamètre) creusé 4 Eau de source 5 Eau de pluie 7 Charrette avec petite citerne/tonneau 10 Eau en sachet 88 Autre
hh_water_tap	byte	HouseHold_WATER_type-of-TAP	1 Robinet dans logement 2 Robinet dans cour/parcelle 3 Robinet public/borne fontaine
hh_water_pit	byte	HouseHold_WATER_type-of-PIT	1 Puits protégé; 2 Puits non protégé

Variable Name	Type	Variable Label	Value Label
hh_water_source	byte	HouseHold_WATER_type-of-SOURCE	1 Source protégée
hh_water_other	str12	HouseHold_WATER_OTHER-source	
hh_l_water	byte	HouseHold_Location-of_WATER-source	1 Dans votre logement; 2 Dans votre cour/parcelle; 3 Ailleurs
hh_t_water	str10	HouseHold_Time-to_WATER-source	
hh_h1_water	byte	HouseHold_H1_WATER-treatment	0 Non; 1 Oui; 99 Ne sait pas
hh_h2_water__1	byte	HouseHold_H2_WATER-treatment__1-boiling	
hh_h2_water__2	byte	HouseHold_H2_WATER-treatment__2-add-bleach-or-chlorine	
hh_h2_water__3	byte	HouseHold_H2_WATER-treatment__3-sprinkle-cement-on-the-surface	
hh_h2_water__4	byte	HouseHold_H2_WATER-treatment__4-cloth-filter	
hh_h2_water__5	byte	HouseHold_H2_WATER-treatment__5-filter-ceramic-sand-composite	
hh_h2_water__6	byte	HouseHold_H2_WATER-treatment__6-solar-disinfection	
hh_h2_water__7	byte	HouseHold_H2_WATER-treatment__7-let-it-stand	
hh_h2_water__88	byte	HouseHold_H2_WATER-treatment__88-other	
hh_h2_water__99	byte	HouseHold_H2_WATER-treatment__99-unknown	
hh_h2_water_other	str1	HouseHold_H2_WATER-treatment__OTHER	
hh_toilet	byte	HouseHold_TOILET	1 Chasse d'eau; 2 Fosse d'aisances; 3 Toilettes à compostage; 5 Toilettes / latrines suspendues; 6 Pas de toilettes/ dans la nature; 88 Autre
hh_toilet_other	str18	HouseHold_TOILET_OTHER-options	
hh_toilet_chasse	byte	HouseHold_TOILET-CHASSE	2 à une fosse septique; 3 à une fosse d'aisance; 5 à ne sait pas où
hh_toilet_fosse	byte	HouseHold_TOILET-FOSSE	2 Fosse d'aisance avec dalle; 3 Fosse d'aisance sans dalle / trou ouvert
hh_s_toilet	byte	HouseHold_Sharing_TOILET-with-others	0 Non; 1 Oui
hh_nr_toilet	byte	HouseHold_total-Number-of-HH-using-the-TOILET	
hh_hyg_water	byte	HouseHold_HYGIENE_WATER-present-at-washing-station	1 Eau disponible; 2 Eau non disponible; 3 Non applicable (pas d'endroit ou possibilité pour laver les mains)
hh_hyg_soap	byte	HouseHold_HYGIENE_SOAP-present-at-washing-station	0 Aucun; 1 Savon ou détergent (en morceau, liquide, poudre, pâte)
hh_floor	byte	HouseHold_FLOOR-material-of-house	1 Terre battue; 2 Ciment; 3 Carreaux, parquet; 4 Linoleum (plastique); 5 Tapis, moquette
hh_floorother	str1	HouseHold_FLOOR-material-OTHER-of-house	
hh_roof	byte	HouseHold_ROOF-material-of-house	1 Tôle (en fer); 2 Banco; 3 Béton; 4 Natte/Paille; 88 Autre
hh_roofother	str8	HouseHold_ROOF-material-OTHER-of-house	
hh_wall	byte	HouseHold_WALL-material-of-house	1 Banco; 2 Semi-dur; 3 Ciment; 4 Pierres; 5 Briques cuites
hh_wallother	str1	HouseHold_WALL-material-of-house	
hh_rooms	byte	HouseHold_number-of-ROOMS	

Variable Name	Type	Variable Label	Value Label
hh_encook	byte	HouseHold_ENergy-for-COOKing	2 Electricité; 3 Gaz; 5 Charbon; 6 Bois; 88 Autre
hh_encookother	str33	HouseHold_ENergy-for-COOKing-OTHER	
hh_enlight	byte	HouseHold_Energy-for-LIGHTning	4 Electricité; 5 Piles (lampe, torche...); 7 Solaire; 10 Batteries (chargées en dehors du ménage); 88 Autre
hh_enlightother	str15	HouseHold_Energy-for-LIGHTning-OTHER	
hh_own	byte	HouseHold_OWnership-of-house	1 Propriétaire; 2 Locataire; 3 Occupation gratuite
hh_inf	byte	HouseHold_best-INFormed-person-on-assets	1 Chef de ménage; 2 La femme ayant accouchée; 88 Autre
hh_infother	str32	HouseHold_best-INFormed-person-on-assets-OTHER	
hh_resp	byte	HouseHold_RESPondent-assets	1 Chef de ménage; 2 La femme ayant accouchée; 88 Autre
hh_respoother	str33	HouseHold_RESPondent-assets-OTHER	
hh_radio	byte	HouseHold_number-of-RADIO	
hh_tv	byte	HouseHold_number-of-TV	
hh_video	byte	HouseHold_number-of-VIDEO-players	
hh_chanel	byte	HouseHold_number-of-CHANEL	
hh_cd	byte	HouseHold_number-of-CD	
hh_mob	byte	HouseHold_number-of-MOBile-phones	
hh_pc	byte	HouseHold_number-of-Personal-Computers	
hh_lamp	byte	HouseHold_number-of-LAMPs	
hh_torche	byte	HouseHold_number-of-TORCHES	
hh_bed	byte	HouseHold_number-of-BEDs	
hh_matras	byte	HouseHold_number-of-MATRAses	
hh_carpet	byte	HouseHold_number-of-CARPETs	
hh_mat	byte	HouseHold_number-of-sleeping-MATs	
hh_prayermat	byte	HouseHold_number-of-PRAYER-MATs	
hh_table	byte	HouseHold_number-of-TABLEs	
hh_chair	byte	HouseHold_number-of-CHAIRs	
hh_armchair	byte	HouseHold_number-of-ARMCHAIRs	
hh_bench	byte	HouseHold_number-of-BENCHes	
hh_stove	byte	HouseHold_number-of-STOVEs	
hh_furnace	byte	HouseHold_number-of-FURNACEs	
hh_cup	byte	HouseHold_number-of-CUPs	
hh_pot	byte	HouseHold_number-of-POTs	
hh_bowl	byte	HouseHold_number-of-BOWLs	
hh_cooktools	int	HouseHold_number-of-COOK-TOOLS	
hh_calabash	byte	HouseHold_number-of-CALABASH	

Variable Name	Type	Variable Label	Value Label
hh_can	byte	HouseHold_number-of-CANs	
hh_iron	byte	HouseHold_number-of-IRONS	
hh_sewing	byte	HouseHold_number-of-SEWING-machines	
hh_watch	byte	HouseHold_number-of-WATCHes	
hh_jewelry	byte	HouseHold_number-of-JEWELRY	
hh_solar	byte	HouseHold_number-of-SOLAR-panels-or-generators	
hh_battery	byte	HouseHold_number-of-BATTERies	
hh_rake	byte	HouseHold_number-of-RAKES	
hh_shovel	byte	HouseHold_number-of-SHOVELs	
hh_sickle	byte	HouseHold_number-of-SICKLEs	
hh_hoe	byte	HouseHold_number-of-HOEs	
hh_pickaxe	byte	HouseHold_number-of-PICKAXES	
hh_axe	byte	HouseHold_number-of-AXES	
hh_wateringcan	byte	HouseHold_number-of-WATERING-CANs	
hh_plow	byte	HouseHold_number-of-PLOWS	
hh_seeder	byte	HouseHold_number-of-SEEDERS	
hh_mill	byte	HouseHold_number-of-MILLS	
hh_motorpomp	byte	HouseHold_number-of-MOTOR-POMPs	
hh_barrow	byte	HouseHold_number-of-BARROws	
hh_agriother	byte	HouseHold_number-of-AGRIcultural-equipment-OTHER	
hh_agriothernames	str8	HouseHold_number-of-AGRIcultural-equipment-OTHER-NAMES	
hh_cart	byte	HouseHold_number-of-CARTs	
hh_bike	byte	HouseHold_number-of-BIKEs	
hh_moto	byte	HouseHold_number-of-MOTOs	
hh_car	byte	HouseHold_number-of-CARs	
hh_tractor	byte	HouseHold_number-of-TRACTORS	
hh_cow	byte	HouseHold_number-of-COWs	
hh_sheep	byte	HouseHold_number-of-SHEEPs	
hh_goat	byte	HouseHold_number-of-GOATs	
hh_donkeyhorse	byte	HouseHold_number-of-DONKEYs-and-HORSEs	
hh_pork	byte	HouseHold_number-of-PORKs	
hh_chicken	int	HouseHold_number-of-CHICKEN	
hh_quinea	byte	HouseHold_number-of-GUINEA-fowl	
dol3_doi_check	str19	Date-Of-Interview_CHECK~Day-Of-Life-3	
dol3_done	byte	did-the-visit-hone~Day-Of-Life-3	0 Non; 1 Oui
dol3_reason_no	byte	REASON-of_NOT-visit~Day-Of-Life-3	
dol3_reason_other	str1	REASON-of_NOT-visit-OTHER~Day-Of-Life-3	
dol3_notes_yn	byte	NOTES-end-of-study_Yes-No~Day-Of-Life-3	0 Non; 1 Oui

Variable Name	Type	Variable Label	Value Label
dol3_notes	str256	NOTES-end-of-study ~Day-Of-Life-3	
dol4_doi	str19	Date-Of-Interview~Day-Of-Life-4	
dol4_idsf	byte	ID-of-Study-midwife~Day-Of-Life-4	5 CA-Assanatou; 6 CA-Aissata; 7 WN; 8 KA; 9 KD; 10 ON; 11 NS; 12 OM
dol4_csps	byte	Centre-de-Sante-et-Promotion-Sociale~Day-Of-Life-4	1 Colma I; 2 Colma II; 3 Farakan; 4 Accart
dol4_w_name	str27	Woman_NAM~Day-Of-Life-4	
dol4_pass1	int	PASSword-1~Day-Of-Life-4	
dol4_pass2	int	PASSword-2~Day-Of-Life-4	
dol4_c_name	str25	Child_NAME~Day-Of-Life-4	
dol4_c_sex	byte	Child_SEX~Day-Of-Life-4	1 M; 2 F
dol4_dom	str10	Date-Of-anthropometry-Measurement~Day-Of-Life-4	
dol4_hom	str7	Hour-Of-anthropometry-Measurement~Day-Of-Life-4	
dol4_weight1	double	child-birth-WEIGHT-1~Day-Of-Life-4	
dol4_weight2	double	child-birth-WEIGHT-2~Day-Of-Life-4	
dol4_weight3	double	child-birth-WEIGHT-3~Day-Of-Life-4	
dol4_bf	byte	exclusive-Breast-Feeding~Day-Of-Life-4	0 Non; 1 Oui
dol4_bf_freq	byte	exclusive-Breast-Feeding_FREQuency~Day-Of-Life-4	1 1-3 fois au cours des dernières 24 heures 2 4-7 fois au cours des dernières 24 heures 3 7-9 fois au cours des dernières 24 heures 4 Plus que 9 fois au cours des dernières 24 heures
dol4_bf_reason	byte	end-exclusive-Breast-Feeding_REASON~Day-Of-Life-4	
dol4_bf_reason_other	str1	end-exclusive-Breast-Feeding_REASON_OTHER~Day-Of-Life-4	
dol4_liq	byte	giving-LIQuids-during-breastfeeding~Day-Of-Life-4	0 Non; 1 Oui
dol4_liq_freq	byte	giving-LIQuids-during-breastfeeding_FREQuency~Day-Of-Life-4	1 1 fois au cours des dernières 24 heures 2 2 fois au cours des dernières 24 heures 3 3 fois au cours des dernières 24 heures 4 Plus que au cours des dernières 24 heures
dol4_solid	byte	giving-SOLIDs-during-breastfeeding~Day-Of-Life-4	0 Non; 1 Oui
dol4_solid_freq	byte	giving-SOLIDs-during-breastfeeding_FREQuency~Day-Of-Life-4	
dol4_temp	double	body-TEMPerature-of-child~Day-Of-Life-4	
dol4_cd1	byte	Child-Disease-1-fever~Day-Of-Life-4	0 Non; 1 Oui
dol4_cd2	byte	Child-Disease-2-diarrhea~Day-Of-Life-4	0 Non; 1 Oui
dol4_cd3	byte	Child-Disease-3-vomit~Day-Of-Life-4	0 Non; 1 Oui
dol4_cd4	byte	Child-Disease-4-cough~Day-Of-Life-4	0 Non; 1 Oui
dol4_cd5	byte	Child-Disease-5-running-nose~Day-Of-Life-4	0 Non; 1 Oui
dol4_cd6	byte	Child-Disease-6-difficult-breathing~Day-Of-Life-4	0 Non; 1 Oui
dol4_cd7	byte	Child-Disease-7-grunting~Day-Of-Life-4	0 Non; 1 Oui
dol4_cd8	byte	Child-Disease-8-skin-lesions~Day-Of-Life-4	0 Non; 1 Oui
dol4_cd9	byte	Child-Disease-9-others~Day-Of-Life-4	0 Non; 1 Oui
dol4_cd9a	str25	morbidity-Child-Disease-9-All~Day-Of-Life-4	

Variable Name	Type	Variable Label	Value Label
dol4_consul__0	byte	morbidity-CONSULT__0-non~Day-Of-Life-4	
dol4_consul__1	byte	morbidity-CONSULT__1-csps~Day-Of-Life-4	
dol4_consul__2	byte	morbidity-CONSULT__2-hospital~Day-Of-Life-4	
dol4_consul__3	byte	morbidity-CONSULT__3-traditional-practitioner~Day-Of-Life-4	
dol4_consul__4	byte	morbidity-CONSULT__4-ASBC~Day-Of-Life-4	
dol4_consul__5	byte	morbidity-CONSULT__5-friend~Day-Of-Life-4	
dol4_consul__6	byte	morbidity-CONSULT__6-family-member~Day-Of-Life-4	
dol4_consul__88	byte	morbidity-CONSULT__88-other~Day-Of-Life-4	
dol4_consul__99	byte	morbidity-CONSULT__99-unknown~Day-Of-Life-4	
dol4_consul_other	str1	morbidity-CONSULT__OTHER~Day-Of-Life-4	
dol4_treat__0	byte	TREATment__0-non~Day-Of-Life-4	
dol4_treat__1	byte	TREATment__1-prescribed-by-health-worker~Day-Of-Life-4	
dol4_treat__2	byte	TREATment__2-self-medication~Day-Of-Life-4	
dol4_treat__3	byte	TREATment__3-traditional-treatment~Day-Of-Life-4	
dol4_treat__4	byte	TREATment__4-treatment-for-malnutrition~Day-Of-Life-4	
dol4_treat__88	byte	TREATment__88-others~Day-Of-Life-4	
dol4_treat_other	str1	TREATment__OTHER~Day-Of-Life-4	
dol4_result	byte	diagnosis-child-morbidity-RESULT~Day-Of-Life-4	1 Traitement toujours en cours; 2 Guéri
dol4_diagn__1	byte	DIAGNosis-child-morbidity__1-malaria~Day-Of-Life-4	
dol4_diagn__2	byte	DIAGNosis-child-morbidity__2-broncho-pneumonia~Day-Of-Life-4	
dol4_diagn__3	byte	DIAGNosis-child-morbidity__3-bacterial/viral/parasitic-diarrhea~Day-Of-Life-4	
dol4_diagn__4	byte	DIAGNosis-child-morbidity__4-dengue-fever~Day-Of-Life-4	
dol4_diagn__5	byte	DIAGNosis-child-morbidity__5-dehydration~Day-Of-Life-4	
dol4_diagn__6	byte	DIAGNosis-child-morbidity__6-malnutrition~Day-Of-Life-4	
dol4_diagn__99	byte	DIAGNosis-child-morbidity__99-unknown~Day-Of-Life-4	
dol4_diagn__88	byte	DIAGNosis-child-morbidity__88-others~Day-Of-Life-4	
dol4_diagn_other	str21	DIAGNosis-child-morbidity__OTHER~Day-Of-Life-4	
dol4_hosp	byte	HOSPitalization-child~Day-Of-Life-4	0 Non
dol4_done	byte	did-the-visit-hone~Day-Of-Life-4	1 Oui
dol4_reason_no	byte	REASON-of_NOT-visit~Day-Of-Life-4	
dol4_reason_other	str1	REASON-of_NOT-visit-OTHER~Day-Of-Life-4	
dol4_notes_yn	byte	NOTES-end-of-study_Yes-No~Day-Of-Life-4	0 Non; 1 Oui
dol4_notes	str198	NOTES-end-of-study ~Day-Of-Life-4	
dol5_doi	str19	Date-Of-Interview~Day-Of-Life-5	
dol5_idsf	byte	ID-of-Study-midwiFe~Day-Of-Life-5	5 CA-Assanatou; 6 CA-Aissata; 7 WN; 8 KA; 9 KD; 10 ON; 11 NS; 12 OM
dol5_csps	byte	Centre-de-Sante-et-Promotion-Sociale~Day-Of-Life-5	1 Colma I; 2 Colma II; 3 Farakan; 4 Accart
dol5_w_name	str27	Woman_NAM~Day-Of-Life-5	

Variable Name	Type	Variable Label	Value Label
dol5_pass1	int	PASSword-1~Day-Of-Life-5	
dol5_pass2	int	PASSword-2~Day-Of-Life-5	
dol5_c_name	str36	Child_NAME~Day-Of-Life-5	
dol5_c_sex	byte	Child_SEX~Day-Of-Life-5	1 M; 2 F
dol5_dom	str10	Date-Of-anthropometry-Measurement~Day-Of-Life-5	
dol5_hom	str5	Hour-Of-anthropometry-Measurement~Day-Of-Life-5	
dol5_weight1	double	child-birth-WEIGHT-1~Day-Of-Life-5	
dol5_weight2	double	child-birth-WEIGHT-2~Day-Of-Life-5	
dol5_weight3	double	child-birth-WEIGHT-3~Day-Of-Life-5	
dol5_bf	byte	exclusive-Breast-Feeding~Day-Of-Life-5	0 Non; 1 Oui
dol5_bf_freq	byte	exclusive-Breast-Feeding_FREQuency~Day-Of-Life-5	1 1-3 fois au cours des dernières 24 heures 2 4-7 fois au cours des dernières 24 heures 3 7-9 fois au cours des dernières 24 heures 4 Plus que 9 fois au cours des dernières 24 heures
dol5_bf_reason	byte	end-exclusive-Breast-Feeding_REASON~Day-Of-Life-5	
dol5_bf_reason_other	str1	end-exclusive-Breast-Feeding_REASON_OTHER~Day-Of-Life-5	
dol5_liq	byte	giving-LIQuids-during-breastfeeding~Day-Of-Life-5	0 Non; 1 Oui
dol5_liq_freq	byte	giving-LIQuids-during-breastfeeding_FREQuency~Day-Of-Life-5	1 1 fois au cours des dernières 24 heures 2 2 fois au cours des dernières 24 heures 3 3 fois au cours des dernières 24 heures 4 Plus que au cours des dernières 24 heures
dol5_solid	byte	giving-SOLIDs-during-breastfeeding~Day-Of-Life-5	0 Non; 1 Oui
dol5_solid_freq	byte	giving-SOLIDs-during-breastfeeding_FREQuency~Day-Of-Life-5	
dol5_temp	double	body-TEMPerature-of-child~Day-Of-Life-5	
dol5_cd1	byte	Child-Disease-1-fever~Day-Of-Life-5	0 Non; 1 Oui
dol5_cd2	byte	Child-Disease-2-diarrhea~Day-Of-Life-5	0 Non; 1 Oui
dol5_cd3	byte	Child-Disease-3-vomit~Day-Of-Life-5	0 Non; 1 Oui
dol5_cd4	byte	Child-Disease-4-cough~Day-Of-Life-5	0 Non; 1 Oui
dol5_cd5	byte	Child-Disease-5-running-nose~Day-Of-Life-5	0 Non; 1 Oui
dol5_cd6	byte	Child-Disease-6-difficult-breathing~Day-Of-Life-5	0 Non; 1 Oui
dol5_cd7	byte	Child-Disease-7-grunting~Day-Of-Life-5	0 Non; 1 Oui
dol5_cd8	byte	Child-Disease-8-skin-lesions~Day-Of-Life-5	0 Non; 1 Oui
dol5_cd9	byte	Child-Disease-9-others~Day-Of-Life-5	0 Non; 1 Oui
dol5_cd9a	str24	morbidity-Child-Disease-9-All~Day-Of-Life-5	
dol5_consul__0	byte	morbidity-CONSULT__0-non~Day-Of-Life-5	
dol5_consul__1	byte	morbidity-CONSULT__1-csps~Day-Of-Life-5	
dol5_consul__2	byte	morbidity-CONSULT__2-hospital~Day-Of-Life-5	
dol5_consul__3	byte	morbidity-CONSULT__3-traditional-practitioner~Day-Of-Life-5	
dol5_consul__4	byte	morbidity-CONSULT__4-ASBC~Day-Of-Life-5	
dol5_consul__5	byte	morbidity-CONSULT__5-friend~Day-Of-Life-5	
dol5_consul__6	byte	morbidity-CONSULT__6-family-member~Day-Of-Life-5	

Variable Name	Type	Variable Label	Value Label
dol5_consul__88	byte	morbidity-CONSULT__88-other~Day-Of-Life-5	
dol5_consul__99	byte	morbidity-CONSULT__99-unknown~Day-Of-Life-5	
dol5_consul_other	str1	morbidity-CONSULT__OTHER~Day-Of-Life-5	
dol5_treat__0	byte	TREATment__0-non~Day-Of-Life-5	
dol5_treat__1	byte	TREATment__1-prescribed-by-health-worker~Day-Of-Life-5	
dol5_treat__2	byte	TREATment__2-self-medication~Day-Of-Life-5	
dol5_treat__3	byte	TREATment__3-traditional-treatment~Day-Of-Life-5	
dol5_treat__4	byte	TREATment__4-treatment-for-malnutrition~Day-Of-Life-5	
dol5_treat__88	byte	TREATment__88-others~Day-Of-Life-5	
dol5_treat_other	str1	TREATment__OTHER~Day-Of-Life-5	
dol5_result	byte	diagnosis-child-morbidity-RESULT~Day-Of-Life-5	1 Traitement toujours en cours; 2 Guéri
dol5_diagn__1	byte	DIAGNosis-child-morbidity__1-malaria~Day-Of-Life-5	
dol5_diagn__2	byte	DIAGNosis-child-morbidity__2-broncho-pneumonia~Day-Of-Life-5	
dol5_diagn__3	byte	DIAGNosis-child-morbidity__3-bacterial/viral/parasitic-diarrhea~Day-Of-Life-5	
dol5_diagn__4	byte	DIAGNosis-child-morbidity__4-dengue-fever~Day-Of-Life-5	
dol5_diagn__5	byte	DIAGNosis-child-morbidity__5-dehydration~Day-Of-Life-5	
dol5_diagn__6	byte	DIAGNosis-child-morbidity__6-malnutrition~Day-Of-Life-5	
dol5_diagn__99	byte	DIAGNosis-child-morbidity__99-unknown~Day-Of-Life-5	
dol5_diagn__88	byte	DIAGNosis-child-morbidity__88-others~Day-Of-Life-5	
dol5_diagn_other	str29	DIAGNosis-child-morbidity__OTHER~Day-Of-Life-5	
dol5_hosp	byte	HOSPitalization-child~Day-Of-Life-5	0 Non
dol5_done	byte	did-the-visit-hone~Day-Of-Life-5	0 Non; 1 Oui
dol5_reason_no	byte	REASON-of_NOT-visit~Day-Of-Life-5	
dol5_reason_other	str1	REASON-of_NOT-visit-OTHER~Day-Of-Life-5	
dol5_notes_yn	byte	NOTES-end-of-study_Yes-No~Day-Of-Life-5	0 Non; 1 Oui
dol5_notes	str202	NOTES-end-of-study ~Day-Of-Life-5	
dol6_doi	str19	Date-Of-Interview~Day-Of-Life-6	
dol6_idsf	byte	ID-of-Study-midwiFe~Day-Of-Life-6	5 CA-Assanatou; 6 CA-Aissata; 7 WN; 8 KA; 9 KD; 10 ON; 11 NS; 12 OM
dol6_csps	byte	Centre-de-Sante-et-Promotion-Sociale~Day-Of-Life-6	1 Colma I; 2 Colma II; 3 Farakan; 4 Accart
dol6_w_name	str27	Woman_NAM~Day-Of-Life-6	
dol6_pass1	int	PASSword-1~Day-Of-Life-6	
dol6_pass2	int	PASSword-2~Day-Of-Life-6	
dol6_c_name	str35	Child_NAME~Day-Of-Life-6	
dol6_c_sex	byte	Child_SEX~Day-Of-Life-6	1 M; 2 F
dol6_dom	str10	Date-Of-anthropometry-Measurement~Day-Of-Life-6	
dol6_hom	str5	Hour-Of-anthropometry-Measurement~Day-Of-Life-6	
dol6_weight1	double	child-birth-WEIGHT-1~Day-Of-Life-6	

Variable Name	Type	Variable Label	Value Label
dol6_weight2	double	child-birth-WEIGHT-2~Day-Of-Life-6	
dol6_weight3	double	child-birth-WEIGHT-3~Day-Of-Life-6	
dol6_bf	byte	exclusive-Breast-Feeding~Day-Of-Life-6	0 Non; 1 Oui
dol6_bf_freq	byte	exclusive-Breast-Feeding_FREQUency~Day-Of-Life-6	1 1-3 fois au cours des dernières 24 heures 2 4-7 fois au cours des dernières 24 heures 3 7-9 fois au cours des dernières 24 heures 4 Plus que 9 fois au cours des dernières 24 heures
dol6_bf_reason	byte	end-exclusive-Breast-Feeding_REASON~Day-Of-Life-6	
dol6_bf_reason_other	str1	end-exclusive-Breast-Feeding_REASON_OTHER~Day-Of-Life-6	
dol6_liq	byte	giving-LIQuids-during-breastfeeding~Day-Of-Life-6	0 Non; 1 Oui
dol6_liq_freq	byte	giving-LIQuids-during-breastfeeding_FREQUency~Day-Of-Life-6	1 1 fois au cours des dernières 24 heures 2 2 fois au cours des dernières 24 heures 3 3 fois au cours des dernières 24 heures 4 Plus que au cours des dernières 24 heures
dol6_solid	byte	giving-SOLIDs-during-breastfeeding~Day-Of-Life-6	0 Non; 1 Oui
dol6_solid_freq	byte	giving-SOLIDs-during-breastfeeding_FREQUency~Day-Of-Life-6	
dol6_temp	double	body-TEMPERature-of-child~Day-Of-Life-6	
dol6_cd1	byte	Child-Disease-1-fever~Day-Of-Life-6	0 Non; 1 Oui
dol6_cd2	byte	Child-Disease-2-diarrhea~Day-Of-Life-6	0 Non; 1 Oui
dol6_cd3	byte	Child-Disease-3-vomit~Day-Of-Life-6	0 Non; 1 Oui
dol6_cd4	byte	Child-Disease-4-cough~Day-Of-Life-6	0 Non; 1 Oui
dol6_cd5	byte	Child-Disease-5-running-nose~Day-Of-Life-6	0 Non; 1 Oui
dol6_cd6	byte	Child-Disease-6-difficult-breathing~Day-Of-Life-6	0 Non; 1 Oui
dol6_cd7	byte	Child-Disease-7-grunting~Day-Of-Life-6	0 Non; 1 Oui
dol6_cd8	byte	Child-Disease-8-skin-lesions~Day-Of-Life-6	0 Non; 1 Oui
dol6_cd9	byte	Child-Disease-9-others~Day-Of-Life-6	0 Non; 1 Oui
dol6_cd9a	str25	morbidity-Child-Disease-9-All~Day-Of-Life-6	
dol6_consul__0	byte	morbidity-CONSULT__0-non~Day-Of-Life-6	
dol6_consul__1	byte	morbidity-CONSULT__1-csps~Day-Of-Life-6	
dol6_consul__2	byte	morbidity-CONSULT__2-hospital~Day-Of-Life-6	
dol6_consul__3	byte	morbidity-CONSULT__3-traditional-practitioner~Day-Of-Life-6	
dol6_consul__4	byte	morbidity-CONSULT__4-ASBC~Day-Of-Life-6	
dol6_consul__5	byte	morbidity-CONSULT__5-friend~Day-Of-Life-6	
dol6_consul__6	byte	morbidity-CONSULT__6-family-member~Day-Of-Life-6	
dol6_consul__88	byte	morbidity-CONSULT__88-other~Day-Of-Life-6	
dol6_consul__99	byte	morbidity-CONSULT__99-unknown~Day-Of-Life-6	
dol6_consul_other	str1	morbidity-CONSULT__OTHER~Day-Of-Life-6	
dol6_treat__0	byte	TREATment__0-non~Day-Of-Life-6	
dol6_treat__1	byte	TREATment__1-prescribed-by-health-worker~Day-Of-Life-6	

Variable Name	Type	Variable Label	Value Label
dol6_treat__2	byte	TREATment__2-self-medication~Day-Of-Life-6	
dol6_treat__3	byte	TREATment__3-traditional-treatment~Day-Of-Life-6	
dol6_treat__4	byte	TREATment__4-treatment-for-malnutrition~Day-Of-Life-6	
dol6_treat__88	byte	TREATment__88-others~Day-Of-Life-6	
dol6_treat_other	str1	TREATment__OTHER~Day-Of-Life-6	
dol6_result	byte	diagnosis-child-morbidity-RESULT~Day-Of-Life-6	1 Traitement toujours en cours; 2 Guéri
dol6_diagn__1	byte	DIAGNosis-child-morbidity__1-malaria~Day-Of-Life-6	
dol6_diagn__2	byte	DIAGNosis-child-morbidity__2-broncho-pneumonia~Day-Of-Life-6	
dol6_diagn__3	byte	DIAGNosis-child-morbidity__3-bacterial/viral/parasitic-diarrhea~Day-Of-Life-6	
dol6_diagn__4	byte	DIAGNosis-child-morbidity__4-dengue-fever~Day-Of-Life-6	
dol6_diagn__5	byte	DIAGNosis-child-morbidity__5-dehydration~Day-Of-Life-6	
dol6_diagn__6	byte	DIAGNosis-child-morbidity__6-malnutrition~Day-Of-Life-6	
dol6_diagn__99	byte	DIAGNosis-child-morbidity__99-unknown~Day-Of-Life-6	
dol6_diagn__88	byte	DIAGNosis-child-morbidity__88-others~Day-Of-Life-6	
dol6_diagn_other	str10	DIAGNosis-child-morbidity__OTHER~Day-Of-Life-6	
dol6_hosp	byte	HOSPitalization-child~Day-Of-Life-6	0 Non
dol6_done	byte	did-the-visit-hone~Day-Of-Life-6	0 Non; 1 Oui
dol6_reason_no	byte	REASON-of_NOT-visit~Day-Of-Life-6	
dol6_reason_other	str1	REASON-of_NOT-visit-OTHER~Day-Of-Life-6	
dol6_notes_yn	byte	NOTES-end-of-study_Yes-No~Day-Of-Life-6	0 Non; 1 Oui
dol6_notes	str171	NOTES-end-of-study ~Day-Of-Life-6	
dol7_doi	str19	Date-Of-Interview~Day-Of-Life-7	
dol7_idsf	byte	ID-of-Study-midwiFe~Day-Of-Life-7	5 CA-Assanatou; 6 CA-Aissata; 7 WN; 8 KA; 9 KD; 10 ON; 11 NS; 12 OM
dol7_csps	byte	Centre-de-Sante-et-Promotion-Sociale~Day-Of-Life-7	1 Colma I; 2 Colma II; 3 Farakan; 4 Accart
dol7_w_name	str27	Woman_NAM~Day-Of-Life-7	
dol7_pass1	int	PASSword-1~Day-Of-Life-7	
dol7_pass2	int	PASSword-2~Day-Of-Life-7	
dol7_c_name	str46	Child_NAME~Day-Of-Life-7	
dol7_c_sex	byte	Child_SEX~Day-Of-Life-7	1 M; 2 F
dol7_dom	str10	Date-Of-anthropometry-Measurement~Day-Of-Life-7	
dol7_hom	str5	Hour-Of-anthropometry-Measurement~Day-Of-Life-7	
dol7_weight1	double	child-birth-WEIGHT-1~Day-Of-Life-7	
dol7_weight2	double	child-birth-WEIGHT-2~Day-Of-Life-7	
dol7_weight3	double	child-birth-WEIGHT-3~Day-Of-Life-7	
dol7_bf	byte	exclusive-Breast-Feeding~Day-Of-Life-7	0 Non; 1 Oui

Variable Name	Type	Variable Label	Value Label
dol7_bf_freq	byte	exclusive-Breast-Feeding_FREQuency~Day-Of-Life-7	1 1-3 fois au cours des dernières 24 heures 2 4-7 fois au cours des dernières 24 heures 3 7-9 fois au cours des dernières 24 heures 4 Plus que 9 fois au cours des dernières 24 heures
dol7_bf_reason	byte	end-exclusive-Breast-Feeding_REASON~Day-Of-Life-7	
dol7_bf_reason_other	str1	end-exclusive-Breast-Feeding_REASON_OTHER~Day-Of-Life-7	
dol7_liq	byte	giving-LIQuids-during-breastfeeding~Day-Of-Life-7	0 Non; 1 Oui
dol7_liq_freq	byte	giving-LIQuids-during-breastfeeding_FREQuency~Day-Of-Life-7	1 1 fois au cours des dernières 24 heures 2 2 fois au cours des dernières 24 heures 3 3 fois au cours des dernières 24 heures 4 Plus que au cours des dernières 24 heures
dol7_solid	byte	giving-SOLIDs-during-breastfeeding~Day-Of-Life-7	0 Non; 1 Oui
dol7_solid_freq	byte	giving-SOLIDs-during-breastfeeding_FREQuency~Day-Of-Life-7	
dol7_temp	double	body-TEMPerature-of-child~Day-Of-Life-7	
dol7_cd1	byte	Child-Disease-1-fever~Day-Of-Life-7	0 Non; 1 Oui
dol7_cd2	byte	Child-Disease-2-diarrhea~Day-Of-Life-7	0 Non; 1 Oui
dol7_cd3	byte	Child-Disease-3-vomit~Day-Of-Life-7	0 Non; 1 Oui
dol7_cd4	byte	Child-Disease-4-cough~Day-Of-Life-7	0 Non; 1 Oui
dol7_cd5	byte	Child-Disease-5-running-nose~Day-Of-Life-7	0 Non; 1 Oui
dol7_cd6	byte	Child-Disease-6-difficult-breathing~Day-Of-Life-7	0 Non; 1 Oui
dol7_cd7	byte	Child-Disease-7-grunting~Day-Of-Life-7	0 Non; 1 Oui
dol7_cd8	byte	Child-Disease-8-skin-lesions~Day-Of-Life-7	0 Non; 1 Oui
dol7_cd9	byte	Child-Disease-9-others~Day-Of-Life-7	0 Non; 1 Oui
dol7_cd9a	str52	morbidity-Child-Disease-9-All~Day-Of-Life-7	
dol7_consul__0	byte	morbidity-CONSULT__0-non~Day-Of-Life-7	
dol7_consul__1	byte	morbidity-CONSULT__1-csps~Day-Of-Life-7	
dol7_consul__2	byte	morbidity-CONSULT__2-hospital~Day-Of-Life-7	
dol7_consul__3	byte	morbidity-CONSULT__3-traditional-practitioner~Day-Of-Life-7	
dol7_consul__4	byte	morbidity-CONSULT__4-ASBC~Day-Of-Life-7	
dol7_consul__5	byte	morbidity-CONSULT__5-friend~Day-Of-Life-7	
dol7_consul__6	byte	morbidity-CONSULT__6-family-member~Day-Of-Life-7	
dol7_consul__88	byte	morbidity-CONSULT__88-other~Day-Of-Life-7	
dol7_consul__99	byte	morbidity-CONSULT__99-unknown~Day-Of-Life-7	
dol7_consul_other	str1	morbidity-CONSULT__OTHER~Day-Of-Life-7	
dol7_treat__0	byte	TREATment__0-non~Day-Of-Life-7	
dol7_treat__1	byte	TREATment__1-prescribed-by-health-worker~Day-Of-Life-7	
dol7_treat__2	byte	TREATment__2-self-medication~Day-Of-Life-7	
dol7_treat__3	byte	TREATment__3-traditional-treatment~Day-Of-Life-7	
dol7_treat__4	byte	TREATment__4-treatment-for-malnutrition~Day-Of-Life-7	

Variable Name	Type	Variable Label	Value Label
dol7_treat_88	byte	TREATment__88-others~Day-Of-Life-7	
dol7_treat_other	str1	TREATment__OTHER~Day-Of-Life-7	
dol7_result	byte	diagnosis-child-morbidity-RESULT~Day-Of-Life-7	1 Traitement toujours en cours; 2 Guéri
dol7_diagn_1	byte	DIAGNosis-child-morbidity__1-malaria~Day-Of-Life-7	
dol7_diagn_2	byte	DIAGNosis-child-morbidity__2-broncho-pneumonia~Day-Of-Life-7	
dol7_diagn_3	byte	DIAGNosis-child-morbidity__3-bacterial/viral/parasitic-diarrhea~Day-Of-Life-7	
dol7_diagn_4	byte	DIAGNosis-child-morbidity__4-dengue-fever~Day-Of-Life-7	
dol7_diagn_5	byte	DIAGNosis-child-morbidity__5-dehydration~Day-Of-Life-7	
dol7_diagn_6	byte	DIAGNosis-child-morbidity__6-malnutrition~Day-Of-Life-7	
dol7_diagn_99	byte	DIAGNosis-child-morbidity__99-unknown~Day-Of-Life-7	
dol7_diagn_88	byte	DIAGNosis-child-morbidity__88-others~Day-Of-Life-7	
dol7_diagn_other	str21	DIAGNosis-child-morbidity__OTHER~Day-Of-Life-7	
dol7_hosp	byte	HOSPitalization-child~Day-Of-Life-7	0 Non
dol7_done	byte	did-the-visit-hone~Day-Of-Life-7	1 Oui
dol7_reason_no	byte	REASON-of_NOT-visit~Day-Of-Life-7	
dol7_reason_other	str1	REASON-of_NOT-visit-OTHER~Day-Of-Life-7	
dol7_notes_yn	byte	NOTES-end-of-study_Yes-No~Day-Of-Life-7	0 Non; 1 Oui
dol7_notes	str240	NOTES-end-of-study ~Day-Of-Life-7	
dol8_doi	str19	Date-Of-Interview~Day-Of-Life-8	
dol8_idsf	byte	ID-of-Study-midwiFe~Day-Of-Life-8	5 CA-Assanatou; 6 CA-Aissata; 7 WN; 8 KA; 9 KD; 10 ON; 11 NS; 12 OM
dol8_csps	byte	Centre-de-Sante-et-Promotion-Sociale~Day-Of-Life-8	1 Colma I; 2 Colma II; 3 Farakan; 4 Accart
dol8_w_name	str27	Woman_NAM~Day-Of-Life-8	
dol8_pass1	int	PASSword-1~Day-Of-Life-8	
dol8_pass2	int	PASSword-2~Day-Of-Life-8	
dol8_c_name	str45	Child_NAME~Day-Of-Life-8	
dol8_c_sex	byte	Child_SEX~Day-Of-Life-8	1 M; 2 F
dol8_done	byte	did-the-visit-hone~Day-Of-Life-8	1 Oui
dol8_reason_no	byte	REASON-of_NOT-visit~Day-Of-Life-8	
dol8_reason_other	str1	REASON-of_NOT-visit-OTHER~Day-Of-Life-8	
dol8_dom	str10	Date-Of-anthropometry-Measurement~Day-Of-Life-8	
dol8_hom	str5	Hour-Of-anthropometry-Measurement~Day-Of-Life-8	
dol8_weight1	double	child-birth-WEIGHT-1~Day-Of-Life-8	
dol8_weight2	double	child-birth-WEIGHT-2~Day-Of-Life-8	
dol8_weight3	double	child-birth-WEIGHT-3~Day-Of-Life-8	
dol8_bf	byte	exclusive-Breast-Feeding~Day-Of-Life-8	0 Non; 1 Oui

Variable Name	Type	Variable Label	Value Label
dol8_bf_freq	byte	exclusive-Breast-Feeding_FREQUency~Day-Of-Life-8	1 1-3 fois au cours des dernières 24 heures 2 4-7 fois au cours des dernières 24 heures 3 7-9 fois au cours des dernières 24 heures 4 Plus que 9 fois au cours des dernières 24 heures
dol8_bf_reason	byte	end-exclusive-Breast-Feeding_REASON~Day-Of-Life-8	1 Difficulté d'allaiter l'enfant
dol8_bf_reason_other	str1	end-exclusive-Breast-Feeding_REASON_OTHER~Day-Of-Life-8	
dol8_liq	byte	giving-LIQuids-during-breastfeeding~Day-Of-Life-8	0 Non; 1 Oui
dol8_liq_freq	byte	giving-LIQuids-during-breastfeeding_FREQUency~Day-Of-Life-8	1 1 fois au cours des dernières 24 heures 2 2 fois au cours des dernières 24 heures 3 3 fois au cours des dernières 24 heures 4 Plus que au cours des dernières 24 heures
dol8_solid	byte	giving-SOLIDs-during-breastfeeding~Day-Of-Life-8	0 Non; 1 Oui
dol8_solid_freq	byte	giving-SOLIDs-during-breastfeeding_FREQUency~Day-Of-Life-8	
dol8_temp	double	body-TEMPERature-of-child~Day-Of-Life-8	
dol8_cd1	byte	Child-Disease-1-fever~Day-Of-Life-8	0 Non; 1 Oui
dol8_cd2	byte	Child-Disease-2-diarrhea~Day-Of-Life-8	0 Non; 1 Oui
dol8_cd3	byte	Child-Disease-3-vomit~Day-Of-Life-8	0 Non; 1 Oui
dol8_cd4	byte	Child-Disease-4-cough~Day-Of-Life-8	0 Non; 1 Oui
dol8_cd5	byte	Child-Disease-5-running-nose~Day-Of-Life-8	0 Non; 1 Oui
dol8_cd6	byte	Child-Disease-6-difficult-breathing~Day-Of-Life-8	0 Non; 1 Oui
dol8_cd7	byte	Child-Disease-7-grunting~Day-Of-Life-8	0 Non; 1 Oui
dol8_cd8	byte	Child-Disease-8-skin-lesions~Day-Of-Life-8	0 Non; 1 Oui
dol8_cd9	byte	Child-Disease-9-others~Day-Of-Life-8	0 Non; 1 Oui
dol8_cd9a	str59	morbidity-Child-Disease-9-All~Day-Of-Life-8	
dol8_consul__0	byte	morbidity-CONSULT__0-non~Day-Of-Life-8	
dol8_consul__1	byte	morbidity-CONSULT__1-csps~Day-Of-Life-8	
dol8_consul__2	byte	morbidity-CONSULT__2-hospital~Day-Of-Life-8	
dol8_consul__3	byte	morbidity-CONSULT__3-traditional-practitioner~Day-Of-Life-8	
dol8_consul__4	byte	morbidity-CONSULT__4-ASBC~Day-Of-Life-8	
dol8_consul__5	byte	morbidity-CONSULT__5-friend~Day-Of-Life-8	
dol8_consul__6	byte	morbidity-CONSULT__6-family-member~Day-Of-Life-8	
dol8_consul__88	byte	morbidity-CONSULT__88-other~Day-Of-Life-8	
dol8_consul__99	byte	morbidity-CONSULT__99-unknown~Day-Of-Life-8	
dol8_consul_other	str1	morbidity-CONSULT__OTHER~Day-Of-Life-8	
dol8_treat__0	byte	TREATment__0-non~Day-Of-Life-8	
dol8_treat__1	byte	TREATment__1-prescribed-by-health-worker~Day-Of-Life-8	
dol8_treat__2	byte	TREATment__2-self-medication~Day-Of-Life-8	
dol8_treat__3	byte	TREATment__3-traditional-treatment~Day-Of-Life-8	
dol8_treat__4	byte	TREATment__4-treatment-for-malnutrition~Day-Of-Life-8	
dol8_treat__88	byte	TREATment__88-others~Day-Of-Life-8	

Variable Name	Type	Variable Label	Value Label
dol8_treat_other	str1	TREATment__OTHER~Day-Of-Life-8	
dol8_result	byte	diagnosis-child-morbidity-RESULT~Day-Of-Life-8	1 Traitement toujours en cours
dol8_diagn_1	byte	DIAGNosis-child-morbidity__1-malaria~Day-Of-Life-8	
dol8_diagn_2	byte	DIAGNosis-child-morbidity__2-broncho-pneumonia~Day-Of-Life-8	
dol8_diagn_3	byte	DIAGNosis-child-morbidity__3-bacterial/viral/parasitic-diarrhea~Day-Of-Life-8	
dol8_diagn_4	byte	DIAGNosis-child-morbidity__4-dengue-fever~Day-Of-Life-8	
dol8_diagn_5	byte	DIAGNosis-child-morbidity__5-dehydration~Day-Of-Life-8	
dol8_diagn_6	byte	DIAGNosis-child-morbidity__6-malnutrition~Day-Of-Life-8	
dol8_diagn_99	byte	DIAGNosis-child-morbidity__99-unknown~Day-Of-Life-8	
dol8_diagn_88	byte	DIAGNosis-child-morbidity__88-others~Day-Of-Life-8	
dol8_diagn_other	str37	DIAGNosis-child-morbidity__OTHER~Day-Of-Life-8	
dol8_hosp	byte	HOSPitalization-child~Day-Of-Life-8	0 Non; 1 Oui
dol8_notes_yn	byte	NOTES-end-of-study_Yes-No~Day-Of-Life-8	0 Non; 1 Oui
dol8_notes	str380	NOTES-end-of-study ~Day-Of-Life-8	
end_interview_key	str11	INTERVIEW__KEY-xx-xx-xx-xx-format~END-of-study	
end_interview_id	str32	INTERVIEW__ID-32-character~END-of-study	
end_doi	str19	Date-Of-Interview~END-of-study	
end_idsf	byte	ID-of-Study-midwiFe~END-of-study	5 CA-Assanatou; 6 CA-Aissata; 7 WN; 8 KA; 10 ON; 11 NS
end_csps	byte	Centre-de-Sante-et-Promotion-Sociale~END-of-study	1 Colma I; 2 Colma II; 3 Farakan; 4 Accart
end_pass1	int	PASSword-1~END-of-study	
end_pass2	int	PASSword-2~END-of-study	
end_w_fname	str9	Woman_First-NAME~END-of-study	
end_w_sname	str9	Woman_Last-NAME~END-of-study	
end_c_name	str16	Child_NAME~END-of-study	
end_c_sex	byte	Child_SEX~END-of-study	1 M; 2 F
end_reason	byte	REASON-for-withdrawal~END-of-study	1 Refus: trop de visites / mesures / questionnaires 2 L'enfant est malade / hospitalisé 4 Déménagement 5 Décès enfant 88 Autre raison
end_reason_other	str37	REASON_OTHER-for-withdrawal~END-of-study	
end_sae_sick	str154	SAE_SICK~END-of-study	
end_sae_child	str28	SAE_CHILD~END-of-study	
end_sae_mother	str1	SAE_MOTHER~END-of-study	
end_date	str10	DATE~END-of-study	
end_day	byte	DAY~END-of-study	2 jour 2; 3 jour 3; 5 jour 5; 6 jour 6; 7 jour 7
end_notes_yn	byte	NOTES_Yes-or-No~END-of-study	0 Non; 1 Oui
end_notes	str94	NOTES~END-of-study	

Variable Name	Type	Variable Label	Value Label
end_sssys_irnd	double	Random-number-in-the-range-0-1-associated-with-interview~END-of-study	
end_has__errors	byte	HAS__how-many-errors~END-of-study	
end_interview__status	byte	INTERVIEW__STATUS~END-of-study	100 Completed
end_assignment__id	int	ASSIGNMENT__ID~END-of-study	